

THE EFFECT OF PARTIAL ZEROING OF HIGH-FREQUENCY WAVELET TRANSFORMATION COEFFICIENTS ON TV IMAGE QUALITY

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***Аннотация.** Данная работа посвящена проблеме повышения эффективности видеокодирования в системах цифрового вещательного и прикладного телевидения на основе минимизации видеоданных. Поэтому оценивается влияние обнуления высокочастотных коэффициентов лифтинговых вейвлет фильтров LeGall (5,3), Deslauriers-Debuc (9,7) и Deslauriers-Debuc (13,7) на качество декодированных ТВ изображений. Приводятся результаты экспериментальных исследований показывающие, как меняется качество тестовых изображений различных сюжетов и жанров вследствие обнуления различных массивов ВЧ вейвлет коэффициентов и их комбинаций.*

***Ключевые слова.** цифровое телевидение, ТВ изображения, видеокодирование, вейвлет преобразования, вейвлет фильтры, вейвлет коэффициенты, качество изображений.*

***Abstract.** The problem of increasing the efficiency of video coding in digital TV and applied television systems due to the minimization of video data is considered in this paper. The effect of zeroing the high-frequency coefficients of the lifting wavelet filters LeGall (5,3), Deslauriers-Debuc (9,7) and Deslauriers-Debuc (13,7) on the quality of decoded TV images is estimated. The results of experimental studies, which show changes in the quality of test images of various video plots due to zeroing high-frequency various arrays of wavelet coefficients and their combinations are presented.*

***Keywords:** digital television, TV images, video coding, wavelet transforms, wavelet filters, wavelet coefficients, image quality*

Introduction

The large screens are increasingly in demand in modern television. The standard definition (SD) videos do not allow obtaining a high-quality image on such type of screens, since the insufficient number of pixels on them will lead to a mosaic structure of frames. That is why the works on the transmission of ultra-high-definition television images in 4K and 8K formats is underway around the world. However, the transition to 4K and 8K formats greatly increases the amount of video data that should be encoded in real time. At the same time, there are about 8.3 megapixels into a 4K format frame with a resolution of 3840×2160, and 33 megapixels into an 8K frame. It requires very high-speed and expensive encoding devices or the use of special methods that significantly minimize the amount of video data of the encoded images. One of such interesting approaches to minimizing video data is the method described in [1]. Its idea is based on bidirectional scaling of images. That is, if before frames' encoding the image sizes are reduced by half, and after decoding them the original image sizes are restored on the receiving side, then the efficiency of video compression in the codec can be significantly increased. This is due to the fact that images reduced by half (horizontally and vertically) contain 4 times less video data, which, on the one hand, allows achieving greater values of video stream compression

with the same image quality. And on the other hand, more accessible computing equipment can be used to process a smaller array of video data. It is especially important for high and ultra-high-definition TV, since it is possible to transmit more high-quality TV programs with more efficient use of the frequency resource.

The statement of problem

Previous studies have shown that good quality of bidirectionally scaled images can be provided by wavelet transforms (WTs), which are scaling functions themselves [2]. However, WT does not change the amount of information in a frame, but only redistributes it between the arrays of low-frequency (LL) and high-frequency (HH) coefficients and their combinations (HL and LH), as shown in Fig. 1. Thus, the total number of coefficients in the low-frequency (LF) and high-frequency (HF) arrays is equal to the number of pixels in the original image. In this case, in the most common WT lifting scheme, the array of LF coefficients contains the most informative part of the reduced by half image, and the array of HF coefficients contains the prediction errors of pixel values [2, 3].

Fig. 1. The structure of the WT coefficients' grouping after the direct two-dimensional transformation of the original image

The conducted studies have shown that acceptable image quality after their bidirectional scaling can be provided by two-dimensional wavelet transforms (WT) with even completely zeroed HF coefficients [4, 5], as shown in Fig. 2, c.

Fig. 2. The original image (a), displaying of the direct WT coefficients (b) and the view of these coefficients with zeroed HF part (c)

However, the problem is that, good quality is provided by this method on relatively smooth images with large objects, as shown in Fig. 3, where the original and restored images are

almost the same. But significant structural distortions may occur on fine-structured images, as shown in Fig. 4.

Fig. 3. The original image (a) and the result of its inverse WT with zeroed HF coefficients (b)

Fig. 4. The original fine-grained image (a) and its distortion due to zeroing of the high-frequency WT coefficients

It is interesting to estimate which type of the HF coefficients should be preserved, to ensure acceptable quality of the displayed images and to improve the image quality after bidirectional scaling.

Experimental Research

For the experimental evaluation of the effect of threshold zeroing of the high-frequency wavelet coefficients, two types of lifting wavelet filters from the Dirac video codec were selected: a short filter on **LeGall (5,3) wavelets** and a long one on **Deslauriers-Debuc (13,7) wavelets** [6]. In this research the generalized algorithm of direct transformation is described by the following expressions [6] :

LeGall (5,3):

$$D_{2i+1} = b_{2i+1} - (b_{2i} + b_{2i+2} + 1) / 2 - \text{HF filter}$$

$$S_{2i} = b_{2i} + (d_{2i-1} + d_{2i+1} + 2)/4 - \text{LF filter}$$

Deslauriers-Debuc (13,7):

$$D_{2i+1} = b_{2i+1} - (((b_{2i} + b_{2i+2}) \times 9 + (b_{2i-2} + b_{2i+4}) \times (-1)) + 8) / 16$$

$$S_{2i} = d_{2i} + ((d_{2i-1} + d_{2i+1}) \times 9 + (d_{i-3} + d_{i+3}) \times (-1) + 16) / 32.$$

Where D and S are the corresponding arrays of high-frequency and low-frequency coefficients, a and b are the pixel values of the image.

And since structural distortions of images most often appear in fine-structured images, then, accordingly, 3 plots with fine-structured images were selected for the experiments. They are presented in Fig. 5.

a)

b)

c)

Fig. 5. A set of test images with high detail, where a) a waterfall, b) a shore, c) a panda

To conduct the experiments, the special codec software with convenient control interface was created on the C++ programming language in the Borland Builder-6 environment. When conducting experimental studies, each test image was first subjected to direct wavelet transformation by the specified wavelet filters; then various threshold values for preserving all high-frequency coefficients were set; after which the inverse WT was performed to analyze the quality of the decoded images. In this case, if the value of the high-frequency coefficients is less than the threshold value, then such a coefficient is preserved, but if it is less than the threshold value, then it will be zeroed.

To evaluate the quality of decoded images, both visual perception and the metric of the root mean square deviation of the pixels from the original and restored images MSE were used. Last one of them described by the following formula [7]:

$$MSE = \frac{1}{mn} \sum_{i=0}^{m-1} \sum_{j=0}^{n-1} |L(i, j) - K(i, j)|^2 \quad (1)$$

where m and n are the horizontal and vertical dimensions of the image. $L(i, j)$ is the value of the pixel of the original image with coordinates (i, j) , and $K(i, j)$ is the value of the pixel of the decoded image with the same coordinates.

If the images match, the MSE value is 0. Accordingly, the metric value increases with increasing distortions in the image. This metric does not correspond to our visual imaginations,

but it allows us to quantitatively evaluate the distortions introduced by different coding algorithms. So it has become widespread.

The obtained results of experimental studies on the assessment of the effect of threshold values of zeroing of the HF WT coefficients on the quality of the reconstructed test television frames are presented in Tables 1 and 2.

Tab.1.

The effect of threshold values for zeroing high-frequency coefficients of LeGall (5,3) wavelet filters on image distortions

Type of images	Values of introduced distortions according to the MSE metric, %											
	Threshold values for zeroing HF coefficients											
	0	10	20	30	40	50	60	70	80	100	150	255
A waterfall	0	3.5	5.5	6.4	6.8	6.9	6.9	6.9	7	7.02	7.04	7.05
A shore	0	2.3	4	5.6	6.9	8	8.8	9.4	9.9	10.4	10.7	10.8
A panda	0	5.2	9.2	12.3	14.4	15.9	16.8	17.5	17.9	18.4	18.8	18.9

Tab 2.

The effect of threshold values for zeroing high-frequency coefficients of Deslauriers-Debuc (13,7) wavelet filters on image distortions

Type of images	Values of introduced distortions according to the MSE metric, %											
	Threshold values for zeroing HF coefficients											
	0	10	20	30	40	50	60	70	80	100	150	255
A waterfall	0	2.5	4.5	5.4	5.8	6	6	6	6.1	6.18	6.2	6.21
A shore	0	2.5	3.2	4.8	5.2	6.1	6.9	7.4	7.9	8.3	8.8	9.1
A panda	0	4.2	8.2	11.1	13.8	14.3	15.2	16.1	16.5	17	17.8	18

As follows from the results of the experiments (Tables 1 and 2), changes in the threshold values by rounding the HF wavelet coefficients allow us to regulate the level of introduced distortions from 0 to the maximum value. But the problem is the small distortion levels are determined by fairly low threshold values (10-30). In this case, a large number of HF coefficients are saved, as shown in Fig. 6. As can be seen from the figure, the array of HF coefficients (HH) continues to contain a large number of these coefficients after threshold processing with a level of 30. And such a large amount of additional information sharply reduces the efficiency of video coding with the use of bidirectional scaling.

Fig. 6. Visualization of arrays of WT coefficients with a threshold value equal to 30

It should also be taken into account that the quality of TV images is primarily determined by the human visual apparatus, which does not always notice the presence of distortions in pixel values; and objective quality assessment metrics are more suitable for comparing the work of various algorithms or encoding modes. Thus, Fig. 7 shows the comparative quality of the original and restored image with completely zeroed HF coefficients. As can be seen from the figure, the original and restored images with $MSE = 18\%$ are visually almost indistinguishable.

Fig. 7. Comparative quality of the original image (a) and image after inverse WT with $MSE = 18\%$ with complete zeroing of HF coefficients (b)

Thus, high values of pixel distortions from zeroing of HF arrays of wavelet coefficients have little effect on the visual quality of displayed images. Therefore, this method of minimizing video data to improve the efficiency of video coding can be applied to TV and applied television systems.

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